

Bohmian Quantum Potential and Momentum Conserving $\exp(ipx)$ Probability

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In (1), it is suggested that a Bohmian quantum potential for a wavefunction $A(x,t) \exp(i S(x,t))$ is given by $(-1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} A)/A$. Here we wish to describe how the notion of such a potential might arise based on viewing the free particle wavefunction as a complex momentum conserving probability.

In a number of previous notes, we argued that one may derive the free particle wavefunction $\exp(ipx)$ by seeking a free particle probability which conserves energy and momentum in Newtonian 2-body (or more) elastic scattering. We argued that for a given initial e_1, e_2 (energies) and p_1, p_2 (momentum vectors), any e_i, e_j and p_i, p_j (vectors) which conserve energy and momentum have equal likelihood of occurring as final outcomes after the collision. This leads to the $\exp(i C_1 E)$ and $\exp(i C_2 p)$ (p along the x -axis) as a solution, but for $p = m_1 v_1 = m_2 v_2$, the same p satisfies a conservation of momentum equation. In a boosted frame, the p 's are different and so do not satisfy the same momentum conserving equation which is a problem, so one requires a Lorentz invariant argument, i.e. $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$. If one only considers momentum, then one has $\exp(ipx)$. In other words, a particle with momentum p and kinetic energy $pp/2m$ (nonrelativistic) is linked with a momentum conserving probability $\exp(ipx)$ which is impulse-centric. Even if one considers kinetic energy $pp/2m$, in the probabilistic view of $\exp(ipx)$, one cannot separate energy from impulse hits as one does in Newtonian mechanics. For example, $pp/2m + V(x) = E$ is strictly about energy. A quantum scenario cannot be so. It must combine both ideas and in this notion of including a picture of impulse hits which gives rise to a kinetic energy term for a bound state (i.e. the Bohmian quantum potential $-1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} A$), which is a statistical average, but at the same time has the appearance of a "potential". In this view, the potential $V(x)$ may be written as $\sum_k V_k \exp(ikx)$ with $\exp(ikx)$ also representing momentum impulse hits, while at the same time V_k represents energy.

Bohmian Quantum Potential

In (1), a Bohmian quantum potential for a wavefunction $W(x,t) = A(x,t) \exp(i S(x,t))$ is given by:

$$-1/2m \left(\frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} A \right) / A \quad ((1))$$

One may note that for a bound state, ((1)) is the average kinetic energy. ((1)) is a statistical quantity, it is not physically realized in a single particle bound state as the particle is either in the state $\exp(ip_1x)$, or $\exp(ip_2x)$ etc. Given that a quantum bound state is like an equilibrium, an average description of all possible results as opposed to a Newtonian deterministic picture is fine. This means then that $V(x)$, the potential, is also seen as an average quantity because one cannot follow any deterministic paths in a quantum picture.

We wish to see how the notion of a Bohmian quantum potential arises as one might argue that ((1)) the average kinetic energy should not be considered as a potential. After all, for a potential one takes $-d/dx V(x)$ to obtain a force and one does not characteristically do this for kinetic energy (even in the average case) even in Newtonian mechanics.

Momentum Conserving Probability for Free Particle Quantum Mechanics

Newtonian mechanics deals both with impulses and energy, but the two are separated. In particular:

$$dp/dt = \text{Force} \quad ((2a)) \quad \text{impulse} = \int F dt \quad ((2b)) \quad \text{and} \quad \text{kinetic energy} = p \cdot p / 2m \quad ((2c))$$

$$\text{with } p(x)p(x)/2m + V(x) = E \quad ((2d))$$

In the case of ((2d)), one only thinks in terms of energy as Force = $-dV/dx$. If one uses $V(x)$ one no longer focuses on force.

In other words, in deterministic Newtonian mechanics one thinks of either impulse hits and force or energy, but not both at the same time.

Interestingly, however, one may consider Newtonian 2-body elastic scattering (or more body) and introduce the notion of probability for both energy and momentum with no potential present. In particular, if one has initial e_1, e_2 energies and p_1, p_2 momentum vectors (along the x axis for simplicity), one might postulate that any e_i, e_j and p_i, p_j (vectors) which conserve energy and momentum have the same probability. This is no longer a deterministic problem, but a probabilistic one and is based on an impulse picture. In other words, kinetic energy is not converted into potential.

At first glance, one might propose

$\exp(i C_1 E)$ and $\exp(i C_2 p)$ (p along the x-axis) as solutions ((3)) with C_1, C_2 being constants for unit purposes

If $p = m_1 v_1 = m_2 v_2$, however, both p particles satisfy a conservation of momentum equation in a certain frame, but not in a boosted frame which is a problem. Thus, we have suggested in previous notes that one introduce a Lorentz invariant probability

$$\exp(-iEt + i p x) \quad (\text{or } \exp(-iEt + i p \cdot r)) \quad ((4))$$

which conserves energy and momentum in any Lorentz boosted frame.

Thus, ((4)) provides a probability for elastic two body collisions. As noted this is probabilistic, not deterministic and one might ask whether ((4)) is useful for any scenario than 2 or many body collisions at a point. We first note that $\exp(ipx)$ implies that there is a spatial uncertainty region of $\hbar/p = dx$ for a p impulse to occur. As a result, this might lead to possible interactions with both slits of a 2-slit apparatus if the slit separation is about \hbar/p . Furthermore, interaction with the atoms/electrons of any given slit should be probabilistic just like a 2-body elastic collision.

The question then becomes: What happens for a potential $V(x)$? In Newtonian mechanics, this is a deterministic problem described by:

$$p^2/2m + V(x) = E \quad ((5))$$

The “catch” is that this deterministic approach requires $dx \rightarrow 0$ and $dt \rightarrow 0$ for interactions. In other words, a particle accelerates in a tiny dx which may be made as small as possible. The probabilistic 2-body approach above, however, sets dx, dt minimal limits:

$$dx = \hbar/p \quad \text{and} \quad dt = \hbar/E \quad ((6))$$

If dx and dt given by ((6)) are tiny with respect to the system length, then Newtonian deterministic physics applies, otherwise it does not and one cannot use ((5)) in a deterministic manner. The notion of conservation of energy and momentum must still apply as it is used to derive ((4)) and so ((5)) should hold at least on average. The point is that any average should be calculated using a probability and the probability available is ((4)) which focuses on impulse hits and momentum conservation even for a $V(x)$ potential situation. One has no choice but to mix an energy viewpoint (e.. $p^2/2m$) with a momentum conserving impulse hit one due to $\exp(ipx)$. Both ideas of energy and impulse hit due to p occur together. Furthermore, this is a probabilistic approach, so an average is a mathematical quantity and not a physical one. A single bound particle can only be in one $\exp(ipx)$ state and so averaging over many $\exp(ipx)$ s yields a math quantity. This math quantity, however, contains various $\exp(ipx)$ s which represent possible momentum impulse hits and so the average kinetic energy has the appearance of a kind of potential (statistical) in that impulse hits are delivered. Furthermore, a bound state in such a case, is like an equilibrium state and one does not need to follow the single particle in time. In such a case, we argue that the notion of an average kinetic energy as a kind of potential appears to be physical. As a result, one may write:

$$-1/2m \left\{ \sum \text{over } p \ a(p) \ p^2/2m \ \exp(ipx) \right\} / \left\{ \sum \text{over } p \ a(p) \ \exp(ipx) \right\} + V(x) = E \quad ((7))$$

Both average kinetic energy and the potential represent energy, but at the same appear as average force fields containing elements $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(ikx)$ (if one writes $V(x) = \sum \text{over } k \ V_k \ \exp(ikx)$) delivering impulse hits.

The main point we wish to make is that the use of $\exp(ipx)$ as a momentum conserving probability implies that one must always think in terms of p impulse hits, even if energy is also being considered in a time-independent problem. The form of average kinetic energy applies to a nonrelativistic scenario, but the idea of mixing energy and impulse-momentum ideas even in a time-independent case, also holds in special relativity. There, one does not have the quantum potential $-1/2m (d/dx d/dx W) / W$ because the problem is relativistic.

Dirac Equation

The Dirac equation in the time-independent case (2) is:

$$(i\partial/\partial t - V(x)) W(x,t) = \hbar \cdot (-i \text{ grad}) W + mc^2 W \quad ((8))$$

In the formalism of (2):

$$a = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & P \\ P & 0 \end{pmatrix} \text{ where } P \text{ is a } 2 \times 2 \text{ Pauli matrix and } b = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix} \text{ is the } 2 \times 2 \text{ identity matrix}$$

Here one does not have the usual Newtonian kinetic energy plus potential energy being total E scenario. In the time-independent case:

$$i \frac{d}{dt} W = E W \quad ((9))$$

and $E \approx m_0 c^2 + \text{kinetic energy}$ in the $v \ll c$ limit. One, however, requires the RHS of ((8)) to become average kinetic energy in the $v \ll c$ limit. In ((8)), it appears as “p” type term which does not look like an energy term, but must be one. Again, the impulse features are contained in the $\exp(ipx)$'s of $W(x)$.

In (2), it is shown explicitly how the RHS of ((8)) becomes average kinetic energy. $W(x)$ is 4-vector composed of two 2-vectors (W_1, W_2). This leads to two equations from ((9)) for W_1 and W_2 in the LHS, using: $\exp(-i m_0 c t)$ as the first approximation to the time dependent portion of W_1 and W_2 .

$$m_0 c^2 W_2 = m_0 c^2 W_2 + P \cdot p W_1 \quad ((10))$$

One may note that the “a” matrices are off anti-diagonal in Pauli matrices P , hence $P \cdot W_1$ with W_2 for the other terms. An equation for W_1 then becomes, following (2):

$$E W_1 = P \cdot p P \cdot p W_1 \quad ((11))$$

E is the free energy, so for a bound state, one may replace it with $E - V(x)$ and then ((11)) becomes the Schrodinger equation. The point is that even the time-independent Dirac equation deals with energy terms (or average energy terms in the bound case because it uses $V(x)$), but impulses are still buried in the $\exp(ipx)$ momentum-conserving parts. Thus, one has once again a hybrid of energy and impulses even in the time-independent case.

Thus, we argue that it is not so much the case of having an explicit extra quantum potential as it is the case that average energy expressions are built from $\exp(ipx)$ probabilities which represent impulse hits and so the average energy expression is automatically a kind of potential in the quantum formalism.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that Newtonian mechanics seems to separate the notions of kinetic-potential energy and impulse hits. For example, impulse hits are described in $dp/dt = \text{Force}$ (impulse = $\int F dt$), whereas energy-potential appears in $pp/2m + V(x) = E$, where $\text{Force} = -d/dx V(x)$.

We have argued in various notes that one may introduce an energy and momentum conserving probability into two body elastic Newtonian scattering. We describe the derivation of this probability above and arrive at $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$. If one has a time-independent problem, then one is left with $\exp(ipx)$ s. The point is that these represent momentum-impulse hits even if the probability is being used to create an average energy. One cannot separate the notions of momentum conserving probabilistic impulse hits and energy. Any average energy quantity is composed of $\exp(ipx)$ s which represent impulse hits and make the statistical quantity have the appearance of a kind of potential in an equilibrium scenario. We argue that this is why one has the appearance of a Bohmian potential: $-1/2m (\frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W(x)) / W(x)$, where $W(x)$ is a single particle bound wavefunction.

References

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